

EdiCitNet News Template

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

EdiCitNet News

Dear all,

Please share the information related to your news using this template. We will use this information to produce news on the Website.

Don't forget to share at least one picture, to make the news more inviting.

News Information

* **News Title:** Please enter here a news title (Example: City Team Meeting in Berlin; EdiCitNet Workshop in Oslo, etc.)

Feel free to be creative !!!

Text of 30 to 150 characters will be accepted

Check it out the novelties of Performance assessment tool for Edible City Solutions (ECS)

* **Description:** Please enter here the text related to the news you are sharing. It can be a local event, meeting or other, related to Edible City Solutions (ECS) and/or EdiCitNet in your cities.

Text of 500 to 2500 characters will be accepted

WP2 team is glad to inform you that the Performance assessment tool, available in the EdiCitNet toolbox web interface (<https://toolbox.edicitnet.com/assessment/>) has been improved.

One of the main novelties is that users can check it out the TOP 10 Edible City Solutions (ECS) in terms of their performance regarding sustainability, urban challenges, and ecosystem services. Moreover, the TOP 10 ECS can also be organized by typology of ECS (e.g. private gardens, community gardens, community kitchens, local markets).

Another novelty is that users can explore the performance of a specific ECS or compare it with other ECS in terms of Sustainability, urban challenges, and ecosystem services. In addition, if you are interested to know more about this ECS, you can easily access their PROFILES from the performance assessment interface. Also, all the data concerning the performance assessment is public available in j.son and excel formats.

WP2 is planning to improve even more the assessment tool. To do so, the tool will allow user to filter ECS per city, and thus explore, compare, and check the top 10 ECS per city.

The performance assessment tool is public and does not require registration to be used. Nevertheless, we kindly invite representatives of Edible City Solutions to create their profiles in the toolbox, and thus help us to expand the edible network, promote knowledge transfer and built together the most compressive database of Edible City Solutions. Please, let us know if you need, we will be glad to help.

Kind regards from WP2 team

Feature Image: Please send an image that will be displayed together with the news.

The maximum file size is 1 MB

Only files of the type png,jpg,jpeg,gif,bmp are allowed

4dabb2cf-3495-4321-b095-c72a1f90065c/Assesment_tool_1.png

Additional Image (Optional): You can share here an additional image that will be displayed in the news.

The maximum file size is 1 MB

Only files of the type png,jpg,jpeg,gif,bmp are allowed

49eb024a-6234-4414-8cdb-943607e8fde2/Assesment_tool_2.PNG

Additional Image (Optional): You can share here an additional image that will be displayed in the news.

The maximum file size is 1 MB

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Hereby I confirm we have the rights to share this picture in EdiCitNet news.

URL: Here you can share an URL related to the news like a link to a video, website, etc.

https://toolbox.edicitnet.com/assessment/

Date: Please confirm the date of the news you are sharing.

21/05/2021

Please specify a location related to the news you are sharing. (City, Address, Venue, etc.)

500 character(s) maximum

Contact Person

* **First and last Name:** Please enter your complete name. It will be displayed as author of the news.

Joana Castellar

* **Organisation:** Please enter the name of your organisation.

ICRA

* **Position:** Please indicate your position in your organisation.

Postdoc

* **City & Country:** Please indicate the city and country where you are contacting us from.

Barcelona, Spain

* **Email:** Your email will not be shown in the news, unless you explicitly indicate it below. We will use it to contact you if we have any question.

jcastellar@icra.cat

I want my Email to be displayed in the news.

- Yes
 No

Social Media

* I agree to share my news on the EdiCitNet Twitter and/or Instagram

- Yes, both of them
- No, none of them
- Only on Twitter
- Only on Instagram

Additional Comments:

500 character(s) maximum

Contact

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